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Environmentally friendly fabrication of electrospun nanofibers made of polycaprolactone, chitosan and κ -carrageenan (PCL/CS/ κ -C)

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Abstract

Electrospun fibers based on biodegradable polyanionic or polycationic biopolymers are highly beneficial for biomedical applications. In this work, electrospun nanofibers made from poly(epsilon caprolactone) (PCL), chitosan (CS) and κ -carrageenan (κ -C) were successfully fabricated using several mixtures of benign solvents containing formic acid and acetic acid. The addition of κ -C improved the preparation procedure for the production of PCL/CS fibers by electrospinning. Moreover, a polymer mixture was selected to be stored at -20°C for one month with the purpose to study the properties of the resulting fiber mat. The results indicated that fiber characteristics were not seriously compromised compared to the ones of those fabricated with the original solution, which represents an important reduction in produced waste. Thus, the interactions that occur between positively and negatively charged hydrophilic polysaccharides might induce higher stability to the linear aliphatic polyester in the polymer mixture. All fiber mats were morphologically, physico-chemically and mechanically characterized, showing average fiber diameters in the nano scale. A direct cell viability assay using ST-2 cells demonstrated cell proliferation after seven days of incubation for all prepared fiber mats, confirming their suitability as potential candidates for bone tissue engineering and wound healing applications.

1. Introduction

Electrospinning is a well-established technology for the preparation of fibrous mats by fabricating fibers of different sizes and using various kinds of polymers. By applying a high-intensity electric field between the polymer solution (or molten polymer) and the grounded collector, a jet of polymer solution (or molten polymer) is generated and eventually deposited on the surface of the collector to form fibers [1–4]. In practice, a variety of factors can affect the morphology and characteristics of fibers, including properties of the solution or melt, parameters of the electrospinning equipment, and environmental factors. The influence of these three groups of factors on the morphology and properties of fibers has been widely investigated [5]. However, the use of new polymers, multiple polymer blends, and solvent mixtures for

electrospinning requires extensive research to reveal the effects of such complex parameters on fiber formation.

Poly(ϵ -caprolactone) (PCL), a synthetic polymer approved by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) for clinical use [6–8], is widely used in the field of biomedical materials, especially as a common polymer for electrospinning processes [9–11]. PCL is characterized by several relevant attributes including good mechanical properties, biodegradability as well as non-cytotoxicity, being beneficial for applications in wound healing, bone- and soft-tissue regeneration, usually blended with other biocompatible polymers, such as collagen [12], gelatin [9, 13, 14] and chitosan (CS) [14, 15].

CS [16] and κ -carrageenan (κ -C)[17] are both polysaccharides of natural origin. CS is also commonly applied as a biomaterial [18–20] because of

its biocompatibility, degradability [21] and antibacterial activity [22]. κ -C, a linear sulfated polysaccharide, is mainly used as an additive in the food industry [17, 23]. Due to its mechanical properties [24], gelation ability [25] and a structure similar to glycosaminoglycans present in the native extracellular matrix (ECM), κ -C has recently started to be investigated as a biomaterial for tissue engineering applications [23, 26]. Furthermore, some studies revealed that anion-rich polysaccharides can modulate the nucleation and growth of hydroxyapatite (HA) crystals through interactions between hydroxyl groups on D-glucosamine ring and HA crystals [27], the chelation of sulfonic groups to Ca^{2+} [28, 29], as well as the formation of hydrogen bonding between sulfonic and phosphate groups and crystal H_2O of HA crystals [28, 29]. Such results indicate that, similarly to bioactive glasses, CS and κ -C may induce the formation of HA under certain conditions, thus expressing bioactivity.

Liverani *et al* [30] reported on the utilization of less toxic or non-toxic benign solvents, such as formic acid (FA) and acetic acid (AA), as a substitute for the traditional toxic solvents used to dissolve PCL for electrospinning. Van der Schueren *et al* [31] also applied an FA/AA solvent system for the preparation of PCL and CS blended nanofibers by electrospinning. Goonoo *et al* [32] and Amjadi *et al* [33] dissolved κ -C and other polymers in polar and non-polar/polar solvent systems for the fabrication of blend nanofibers by electrospinning.

The aim of this study is to enhance the biodegradability of PCL through incorporation of marine polysaccharides of different nature such as κ -C and high molecular weight (HMW) CS, based on the results of a previous work where 3D hybrid scaffolds from these polysaccharides were fabricated [34], as well as to avoid the presence of traces of toxic solvents in the obtained fibers, having a positive impact on laboratory workers safety and waste management. In addition, the work intends to enhance the mechanical properties of electrospun fibers fabricated from formulations containing polysaccharides and to evaluate any potential bioactive response of the fibers without incorporating other agents or fillers. Finally, this work includes a preliminary cell viability assay to study the behavior of fiber mats obtained from a solution that was stored for 30 days, in comparison to the original ones to assess the shelf-life capability of the used polymer solution.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Preparation of the polymer solution and electrospinning process

The synthesis of novel electrospun nanofibers was based on a previously published protocol by Liverani *et al* [15], about PCL/CS fibers. Briefly, 0.6% (w/v) of

κ -C (sulfated plant polysaccharide, Sigma Aldrich®) was dissolved in different ratios of a hot mixture of FA (98%, VWR Chemicals, Germany) and AA (99% GPR RECTAPUR®, VWR, Darmstadt, Germany) at 70 °C. Once κ -C was completely dissolved, the solution was cooled down to room temperature. After that, 6% (w/v) of PCL ($(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2)_n$, Mn \sim 80 000, Sigma Aldrich®, Munich, Germany), was added into the solution under continuous magnetic stirring until a homogeneous solution was obtained. Then, CS (deacetylated chitin, HMW, Sigma Aldrich®) was incorporated into the mixture in a weight ratio of 20% with respect to the amount of PCL and the final mixture was left under magnetic stirring overnight. Subsequently, the slightly yellow solution was sonicated for 15 min and left standing for another 30 min before electrospinning. Accordingly, sonication was performed using a Vibracell CV 33 sonicator (20 kHz Sonics & Materials) fitted with a 3 mm diameter titanium microtip. An amplitude of 10% with a 2 s ON and 3 s OFF for 1.5 min with a total duration time of 15 min was determined for the homogenization of the polymer solution. Between each interval, the solution was ultrasonicated for 1 min and slowly stirred for another 2 min. Table 1 shows the ratios of the acid mixtures that were used to prepare different nanofibers.

To study the stability and degradation resistance of the novel polymeric mixture, the solution with a ratio of 7:3 FA/AA was kept at -20 °C for different periods of time (3, 7, 14 and 30 days). Only the fiber mats prepared after the longest storage period of 30 days were fully analyzed for comparison. For this, the solution was kept under ambient conditions until reaching the room temperature and then it was lightly stirred for 1 h. Finally, it was sonicated for 15 min and left for another 30 min without stirring before electrospinning. The experiment was performed in triplicate to verify its reproducibility.

The electrospinning process was performed at room temperature, using a commercial apparatus (Starter Kit, Linari Engineering S.r.l., Italy). The solution was poured into a 3 ml plastic syringe, which was connected to a pump and fed through a 21 G needle at a feed rate of 0.3 ml h^{-1} , using high DC voltages of 15 and 20 kV (Gamma High Voltage generator). The electrospun fibers were collected on the aluminum foil surface after a charged polymer jet from the needle was produced by a strong electric field at the tip of the needle to form a continuous fiber that was driven to the collector.

2.2. Morphological and chemical characterization

The morphology of the fiber mats was characterized by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (FE-SEM, Auriga, Carl-Zeiss, Jena, Germany) at different magnifications. Prior to the SEM analysis, the samples were sputtered with gold using a sputter

Table 1. Designated names of the nanofibers made from PCL/CS/ κ -C based on different ratios of the acid mixture of formic acid (FA) and acetic acid (AA) and the electrospinning parameters. The sample NF7:3_20 was fabricated using the voltage of 20 kV. The sample NF7:3_30D was produced from the solution NF7:3 after being stored for 30 days at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Samples	FA:AA ratio	kV	Flow rate (ml h ⁻¹)	Time (h)	Distance (cm)	Temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	Humidity (%)
NF3:7	3:7	15	0.3	4	10	23.8	26
NF1:1	1:1	15	0.3	4	10	24.4	24
NF7:3	7:3	15	0.3	4	10	23.8	25
NF7:3_20	7:3	20	0.3	4	10	23.5	26
NF7:3_30D	7:3	15	0.3	4	10	25.3	51

coater (Q150T, Quorum Technologies Ltd, Germany). ImageJ-Fiji 1.51 analysis software [35] (NIH, Bethesda, MD, USA) was used to randomly select and analyze 500 fibers per sample to calculate the average fiber diameter. Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, employing the attenuated total reflectance (ATR-FTIR) (IRAffinity-1S, Shimadzu) was performed to determine the chemical structure of the fiber mats. Forty spectral scans in the range of $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} were carried out to obtain the measurements. To study the wettability of the fiber mats, static water contact angle in air was measured by dropping $3\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ of deionized water onto the fiber mats (sessile drop method, DSA30, Kruss GmbH, Hamburg, Germany). To obtain the average contact angle value, five samples of each fiber mat were measured at room temperature. The data was collected by DSA software (DSA4 2.0, Kruss GmbH, Hamburg, Germany).

2.3. Mechanical characterization

The mechanical properties of the fibrous specimen at room temperature were assessed by standard uniaxial tensile test (5967 Dual Column Tabletop Testing System, Instron®, Darmstadt, Germany). Fiber mats were cut into rectangular strips with a length of 20 mm and a width of 5 mm. The thickness of the specimens was measured using a precision micrometer (Schut Geometrical Metrology, Germany), having thickness values in the range $7\text{--}12\text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The cut fiber mat strips were fixed into paper frames with double-sided adhesive tape to protect them against ripping due to the clippers of the machine. Mechanical tests were conducted with a crosshead velocity of 1 mm min^{-1} using a 50 N load cell. All tests were carried out at room temperature and repeated for each specimen five times. Young's modulus (E), failure strain (FS) and ultimate tensile strength (UTS) values were obtained from the stress-strain curves.

2.4. Bioactivity and degradation tests

The *in vitro* bioactivity of the electrospun fiber mats was performed by using customized 3D printed polycarbonate cylindrical holders (diameter around 1 cm). The samples on the holders were immersed in simulated body fluid (SBF), based on the methodology previously reported by Kokubo and

Takadama [36]. The samples were incubated (KS 4000i control, IKA, Germany) under physiological conditions ($37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 90 rpm) for 1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days. After immersion at each time point, the pH of the solution was measured, and the samples were gently rinsed with deionized water before drying at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ overnight. Finally, the fiber mats were characterized by SEM, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDX) and FTIR.

Due to the similarity to NF7:3 and NF7:3_30D, the NF7:3_20 sample was used as a reference for degradation tests following a reported procedure [37] with some modifications. The assay was performed in triplicate. The sample was immersed in a previously prepared Tris-HCl buffer solution (1 M, pH = 7.4) under physiological conditions ($37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 90 rpm) for 7, 14 and 30 days. The Tris-HCl solution was renewed every seven days. The resulted fiber mats were analyzed by SEM and FTIR. The same holders described above were employed.

2.5. Cell culture

ST-2 cells, a mouse stromal cell line, were purchased from Leibniz Institute DSMZ – German Collection of Microorganisms and Cell Cultures GmbH, Germany. The viability of cells was assessed by using the WST-8 assay (Cell Counting Kit-8, Sigma-Aldrich). Fiber mats were mounted onto Cellcrown™ 24 (Scaffdex, Tampere, Finland) prior to disinfection and placed in individual wells of a 24-well plate. The samples were disinfected using 70% v/v aqueous ethanol (EtOH) under UV light for 30 min, washed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) buffer solution and exposed to UV light with Roswell Park Memorial Institute (RPMI) cell culture medium for further 30 min before cell seeding. Each scaffold was seeded with $100\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ of standard RPMI culture medium (RPMI 1640, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA) supplemented with 10 v.% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (FBS Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA) and 1 v.% penicillin-streptomycin (Penicillin-Streptomycin 5000 U ml⁻¹ Gibco, Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc., USA) containing 1.5×10^4 cells and incubated for 30 min before added another $900\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ of medium. The cells were cultured for seven days, in an incubator with a humidified atmosphere maintained at $37\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 5% CO₂ to study the overall initial

cell behavior. After the time point of interest, the culture medium was removed from the respective well culture plate, and the samples were washed with PBS. After addition of the WST-8 (1 v/v% in colorless RPMI) in each well, the plates were incubated for three hours. Subsequently, the supernatant of all samples was transferred to a 96-well plate (100 μ l in each well) to measure the absorbance at 450 nm with a Micro-Reader (Perkin Elmer, Multilabel Reader Enspire 2300, Germany). The results were expressed as a percentage of the mean absorbance (optical density at 450 nm) in quintuplicate. The cytoskeletal F-actin, as well as the nuclei of ST-2 cells were stained using rhodamine phalloidin and 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) (Thermo Scientific, Germany), respectively. Living ST-2 cells were revealed by calcein acetoxymethyl ester (Calcein AM, Invitrogen, Life Technologies, Germany) staining. Fluorescence micrographs were taken using a fluorescence microscope (Axio Scope.A1, Carl Zeiss, Germany).

2.6. Statistical analysis

For statistical analysis of cell viability results, the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used, which is implemented in Origin 2020 (OriginLab Corporation, Northampton, USA) software. The number of samples was $N = 5$ for all studies. The significance level was set as $p^* < 0.05$. For the comparison of the mean values with ANOVA, the Tukey post-hoc test was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Fiber morphology

SEM micrographs at different magnifications show randomly oriented fibers with diameters in the nano-scale. The polymer mixture made from a biodegradable and elastic polyester combined with two strongly interacting biodegradable polysaccharides originated fibers with diameter sizes that can range from 160 nm to 10 nm independently from the ratio of the acid mixture (solvent). Figures 1(A) and (B), at the lowest magnification, illustrate the presence of beads. The number of beads proportionally increased with the concentration of AA in the mixture. Figures 1(C)–(E) illustrate a further formation of branched fibers with smaller diameters as reflected in the fiber diameter distributions, where a considerable contribution from these small fibers is present. These meshes were synthesized using the same ratio of FA/AA (7:3), which explains the great similarity between them. At a FA/AA ratio of 7:3, the solution changed color to pale yellow, suggesting better incorporation of CS that contributed to increasing electrostatic interactions during the electrospinning process, resulting in the formation of fibers with smaller diameter. A similar color was observed by Zhang *et al* [38] after mixing CS with dilute acid aqueous solution.

3.2. Chemical characterization

FTIR spectra of fiber mats made from PCL, CS and κ -C using different ratios of FA/AA are shown in figure 2(A). Absorption bands at 2943 and 2868 cm^{-1} represent symmetric and asymmetric stretching of C–H, respectively. These bands are mainly attributed to PCL [30, 39], but can also be related to CS [15, 40] and κ -C [41]. High-intensity signature bands of ester groups of PCL are observed at 1720 cm^{-1} and 1165 cm^{-1} , which are associated with carbonyl stretching vibration and asymmetric stretching vibration of the C–O–C bridge, respectively. The group of bands around 1595 cm^{-1} corresponds to N–H bending vibration of amide II of CS [40]. The signals at 1419 cm^{-1} and 1362 cm^{-1} are due to the C–O–H in-plane bending vibration mode and C–H bending vibration mode, respectively. The peak centered at 1294 cm^{-1} is ascribable to backbone C–O and C–C stretching vibration. The bands at 1044 cm^{-1} correspond to C–O stretching vibration. The representative bands of κ -C at 1237 cm^{-1} and 840 cm^{-1} are related to the O=S=O stretching vibration mode and the –O–SO₃ stretching vibration mode at the C-4 position of galactose, respectively [41]. Moreover, the absorption peak at 933 cm^{-1} is attributed to the C–O–C vibration mode of the 3,6-anhydro-D-galactose residue [41]. Finally, the highly characteristic N–H bending vibration mode, corresponding to torsion of amines I and II in CS could be associated with the peak at 620 cm^{-1} . The band in the region 3200–3600 cm^{-1} , corresponding to N–H and O–H stretching, is barely evident. The spectrum of NF7:3_30D, analyzed after 30 days, is identical to the NF7:3 spectrum, demonstrating that the original solution was not affected by the storage. No distinct degradation or transformation of the final product was observed, which suggests that the mixture of both polysaccharides with PCL provided stability to the polymer solution when the ratio of FA:AA was 7:3.

3.3. Mechanical properties and wettability

For the use in tissue engineering, electrospun nanofibers have attracted great attention due to their unique features, including biocompatibility, degradability and, particularly, their fibrous structure that could, in some cases, mimic the ECM morphology [42]. However, indispensable mechanical properties need to be achieved. Tensile strength tests were therefore performed on the fiber mats to investigate their mechanical properties for the success of the tissue engineering strategy. Data obtained from stress–strain curves are reported in table 2, reporting Young's modulus (E), UTS and failure strain (FS). Figure 2(B) shows that the E and UTS values significantly increased by increasing the amount of FA in the mixture, which can be related to a higher integration of the polysaccharides into the polymer solution in comparison to samples prepared at lower FA concentrations. No significant difference was recorded

between the samples electrospun at a voltage of 15 kV or 20 kV using a solution with the 7:3 FA:AA ratio. The reduced mechanical properties of NF7:3_30D can be related to both the storage conditions and the relative humidity, being the only sample that was

produced under higher values of relative humidity in the electrospinning chamber. Accordingly, the evaporation of the solvent is slower due to the competition with water adsorption on the polymer, leaving the polymer jet exposed to voltage-induced stretching

Table 2. Fiber diameter, contact angle measurements results and mechanical properties of the electrospun fiber mats made of polycaprolactone, chitosan and κ -carrageenan (PCL/CS/ κ -C). UTS: ultimate tensile strength.

	NF3:7	NF1:1	NF7:3	NF7:3_20	NF7:3_30D
Average fiber diameter (nm)	49 ± 16	64 ± 19	59 ± 14	65 ± 13	56 ± 13
Contact angle (°)	113 ± 14	103 ± 10	89 ± 9	83 ± 3	92 ± 8
Young's modulus (MPa)	18 ± 6	21 ± 6	90 ± 19	68 ± 9	58 ± 8
UTS (MPa)	8 ± 1	9 ± 4	14 ± 3	11 ± 4	9 ± 3
Strain to failure (%)	56 ± 7	66 ± 11	33 ± 6	34 ± 15	21 ± 4

for a longer period, which resulted in thinner nanofibers [43]. Consequently, fibers with diameters below 20 nm were obtained, which is consistent with SEM micrographs. Thinner nanofibers have short-length branches that are not interconnected, impairing the mechanical properties. Moreover, the storage conditions could have also affected the mechanical resistance due to the possible partial degradation of PCL. Indeed Van der Schueren *et al* [44] reported that a polymer solution containing 14 wt.% PCL in 40 v% AA was degraded after three hours of having been stored. Nevertheless, the negatively charged molecular chains of κ -C that electrostatically bonded to the positively charged molecular chains of CS might have improved the degradability of PCL when a FA/AA solution in a 7:3 ratio was used. Consequently, better incorporation of CS and κ -C into the polymer blend with a ratio of 7:3 (FA/AA) also reduced the failure strain, causing elongation at break to decrease as a result of increased brittleness. A similar result was reported by Liu *et al* [45], showing that the failure strain (%) increased when the proportion of CS to PLA decreased. Overall, the addition of κ -C to the polymer mixture containing PCL and HMW CS considerably

increased the E values compared to those obtained by Liverani *et al* [15] for PCL/CS electrospun fiber mats with an E average value of 3 ± 1 MPa. In this regard, the incorporation of HMW CS and the sulfated polysaccharide produced electrostatic interactions that, together with PCL, enhanced the mechanical properties of the final fiber mats.

From a tissue engineering perspective, the main concern is associated with the hydrophobic behavior of most electrospun synthetic polymers, which in most cases negatively affects their biological properties [42]. Thus, wettability not only depends on surface roughness and chemical composition but also on other parameters and conditions related to the electrospinning process, which can significantly alter the protein deposition, degradation rate and most importantly, cell adhesion processes [39]. In this sense, a favorable design of fibers with a suitable morphology and chemical composition is essential to provide an adequate scaffolding for cell growth and to facilitate cell-surface interactions [42]. Therefore, the incorporation of two hydrophilic biopolymers with different nature might contribute to enhance the wettability and surface functionality of

Figure 3. SEM micrographs of nanofiber mats made from PCL/CS/ κ -C after being immersed in SBF for 21 days, (A) NF3:7, (B) NF1:1, (C) NF7:3 and (D) NF7:3_30D. The dotted-white circles represent zones where beads are located.

the fibrous structures when an adequate acid mixture is employed. Figure 2(C) shows the results of water contact angle measurements that were determined to study the wettability of electrospun fiber mats. All measured contact angles are reported in table 2. The surfaces of samples NF3:7 and NF1:1 prepared from a polymer solution with a higher content of AA were hydrophobic, with average contact angles above 100° . However, when the content of FA increased during the polymer solution preparation, the resulting nanofibers showed a reduced contact angle of around 90° . Thus, materials fabricated using a PCL/CS/ κ -C solution at a FA/AA ratio of 7:3 presented an improved wettability compared to fibers produced from other ratio mixtures. All samples exhibited a hydrophobic or slightly hydrophobic behavior compared to the contact angle range reported by Arima and Iwata [46] (between 70° and 40°) considered suitable for effective cell adhesion on the polymer fiber mats.

3.4. Bioactivity and degradation tests

To study *in vitro* bioactivity, the PCL/CS/ κ -C fiber mats were immersed in SBF for 1, 3, 7, 14 and 21 days and incubated in a shaking-incubator under physiological conditions of 37°C and 90 rpm. The samples were analyzed by SEM, EDX mapping and ATR/FTIR spectroscopy. Figure 3 shows SEM micrographs of fiber mats synthesized by using different ratios of FA and AA after 21 days of incubation in SBF. No deposits were observed in NF3:7 and NF1:1 samples (figures 3(A) and (B)). The scaffolds kept their fibrillar structure, however, a significant amount of beads was observed. These beads were originally positioned within the fiber mats, however, after 21 days of immersion in SBF they were easier

to identify due to the soaking and adhesion of the fibers. In the samples prepared at a 7:3 FA:AA ratio (figures 3(C) and (D)), a layer of nanoparticles was deposited on the fibers. The nanoparticles were visible from the third day onwards. The NF7:3_30D mesh, fabricated from the polymer solution stored at -20°C for 30 days, showed similar behavior than NF7:3. Nonetheless, the layer formed on NF7:3_30D was thicker and covered a larger surface of fibers, which suggests a higher bioactive response. This behavior could be attributed to a higher concentration of polysaccharides due to a partial degradation of PCL, which could also partly explain the decrease in mechanical properties discussed above. Accordingly, Baskar *et al* [47] have reported mineralization occurring from pristine CS films upon immersion in SBF. They observed deposits similar to those detected in this work. It was proposed that the cationic and hydrophilic nature of chitosan could have triggered the nucleation for mineralization after immersion of CS films in SBF for three weeks at 37°C . The adsorption of PO_4^{3-} ions could have been induced by the presence of $-\text{NH}_2$ groups. Thus, acetylation influenced the initial calcium distribution on the CS surface, producing deposits of calcium phosphates (HA). Usually, the bioactivity in electrospun fibers is associated with the incorporation of different types of bioactive materials such as bioactive glass [15] and HA [48], inducing the formation of apatite structures when in contact with SBF solution. The present results proved that the ratios of the acid mixture based on FA and AA could play a major role by tuning the properties of the final nanofibers.

EDX mapping was carried out to corroborate the nature of the particle layer deposited on

Figure 4. (A) SEM image, EDX spectrum, and element mapping micrographs for C (red), O (green) and their merged image of NF7:3_30D samples after immersion in SBF for 21 days and (B) FTIR spectra of NF7:3_30D samples after immersion in SBF for 7 and 21 days. The bands highlighted in blue correspond to the functional groups associated to the formation of calcium phosphate. The rest of the peaks in the EDX spectrum are attributed to the sample holder, where the highest intensity corresponds to aluminum with remnants of Cu and Ag that were not adequately removed. The abbreviation CS denotes chitosan.

NF7:3_30D after immersion in SBF solution for 21 days. Figure 4(A) exhibits the elemental composition of the particles, being mainly composed of carbon (C) and oxygen (O), exhibiting a composition similar to the fiber mats. A partial transformation of the fibers into a layer of particles might have occurred due to the partial release or degradation of CS and κ -C since a similar layer of CS nanoparticles was observed by Agarwal *et al* [49]. A low intensity peak in the EDX spectra confirmed the presence of phosphorus (P) and calcium (Ca), indicating that the PCL/CS/ κ -C nanofibers synthesized from a solution that contained FA and AA in a ratio of 7:3 could promote a bioactive response (mineralization) when in contact with SBF solution over time. The Ca/P ratio was qualitatively determined to have a value close to 1, which suggests the formation of either anhydrous dicalcium phosphate (DCPA) or its

dihydrate form (DCPD) [50], which may be considered as an intermediate step towards HA formation [51]. The same behavior was confirmed by the ATR/FTIR spectra (figure 4(B)), where similar bands as in the original material were observed. However, two bands at 525 and 586 cm⁻¹ were detected after seven days of immersion in SBF, which can be related to the symmetric stretching vibration $\nu_4(\text{PO}_4^{3-})$. The bands at 1055 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to phosphate $\nu_3(\text{PO}_4^{3-})$. The peaks at 1652 cm⁻¹ and 1559 cm⁻¹ can be attributed to the amide (CONH₂) and amine (NH₂) bands, respectively [52]. Bands that are present in CS, which could better explain the nature of the particulate layer observed by SEM. The broad band between 3200 and 3500 cm⁻¹ corresponds to the stretching vibration of hydroxyl (–O–H) and amine (–N–H) groups that can be associated with CS or with hydroxyl groups

Figure 5. (A) SEM micrographs of NF7:3_20 nanofiber mats at different magnifications after being immersed in Tris-HCl buffer for (A) 7 days, (B) 14 days and (C) 30 days. The bands highlighted in blue correspond to the functional groups associated to the formation of calcium phosphate and the partial degradation of chitosan in the fibers. Dotted-white circles indicate zones where the spherical particles are located (discussed in the text). (D) FTIR spectra of NF7:3_30D samples after immersion in Tris-HCl for 14 and 30 days. CS corresponds to chitosan.

related to the formation of calcium phosphates [53].

The physicochemical characterization of nanofiber mats produced from a solution containing FA and AA in the ratio of 7:3 demonstrated similar properties, independently of the conditions employed for their fabrication. In this regard, a degradation test using Tris-HCl buffer was performed to study the

response of the NF7:3_20 sample, when it was in contact with a medium where no ions originating from salts were present. Tris-HCl buffer was chosen because of its importance in biomedicine, being frequently used for *in vitro* degradation [54] and enzymatic degradation tests [55].

SEM micrographs in figure 5 show absorption of the buffer solution by the fibers after 7, 14 and

30 days of immersion. The swelling allowed to clearly distinguish the two groups of fibers of different sizes originally observed in all the NF7:3 samples (figure 1). The same behavior as in the SBF test was observed on day 7 of the test, when a layer of nanoparticles appeared. After 14 days, two different regions emerged, one where the fibrillar structure was kept, and a second where the fibers started to degrade, transforming into a film. The presence of spherical nanoparticles with diameters in the range of 100–150 nm is also visible. After 30 days, the fibers located originally on the external surface visibly degraded, creating a porous membrane with some fibrillar structures still being present. Interestingly, some spherical nanoparticles appear to be emerging from the film. FTIR spectra, reported in figure 5(D), show the presence of the same bands observed in figure 4(B) from the SBF assay. The bands located between 1490 and 1680 cm^{-1} associated with the amide and amine groups of the CS can be clearly observed when the spectrum is magnified. In addition to the bands discussed above, two new peaks are observed at 798 and 884 cm^{-1} , which can be attributed to the presence of symmetric $\nu_4(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$ and asymmetric $\nu_2(\text{CO}_3^{2-})$ vibration modes, respectively [56].

To understand the degradability of NF7:3₂₀, it is necessary to discuss in depth the hydrolysis process of PCL in similar solvent systems. In this regard, Ekram *et al* [57] studied the degradation of electrospun PCL fibers produced using an FA/AA solvent system (70:30). The degradation in PBS of the polyester occurred through the hydrolysis of the labile aliphatic ester linkages, originating shorter water-soluble fragments from the original long PCL chains. However, the degradation rate was very low under physiological conditions. Additionally, the authors reported changes in viscosity as a function of time of the PCL solution (15 wt%) at 22 °C [57]. The FA/AA system caused a significant decrease in viscosity due to PCL hydrolysis under these acidic conditions, negatively affecting the production of electrospun PCL after a short period of time. In accordance, Lavielle *et al* [58] studied the degradation process of electrospun PCL fibers fabricated from a solution containing 20% (w/v) PCL in a mixture of FA/AA with a ratio of 50/50 (v/v). The electrospinning process was carried out using different time periods after solution preparation (24, 48, 72, 96, 168 and 264 h). The results showed that the molecular weight (Mn) decreased from 65 to 10 kg mol^{-1} , while the polydispersity increased due to hydrolytic degradation at room temperature of the polyester solution catalyzed by the acid conditions. Similar to the previous studies and to the investigation of Van der Schueren *et al* [44], Ghobeira *et al* [59] observed that a PCL solution containing 14 wt% PCL in a AA/FA (10/90) solvent system considerably degraded in the first 24 h after preparation, resulting in a decrease in molecular

Figure 6. Results of WST-8 measurements after three and seven days of ST-2 cells seeded on NF7:3, NF7:3₂₀ and NF7:3_{30D} PCL/CS/κ-C fiber mats, respectively. * $p < 0.05$.

weight and thus in solution viscosity over time. The quality of the electrospun fibers after 24 h decreased considerably, obtaining broken fibers full of beads. This result was due to a drastic loss in the cohesion of the solution, which could not withstand the strong deformations and stresses developed during the spinning process. In summary, we could infer faster degradation of electrospun PCL/CS/κ-C fibers after immersion in Tris-HCl at physiological pH compared to those immersed in PBS, where only PCL was used. In this sense, the incorporation of a natural polysaccharide system improved not only the degradation behavior and hydrophilicity but also the storage time of the polymer solution.

3.5. Direct cell viability test

ST-2 cells were seeded on NF7:3, NF7:3₂₀ and NF7:3_{30D} to investigate the influence of different voltages (15 kV vs 20 kV) applied for electrospinning, as well as to test the suitability of the fibers mat fabricated with the polymer solution stored for 30 days at -20 °C on the cell behavior. The viability of ST-2 cells seeded on the samples was measured by WST-8 kit. As indicated by figure 6, NF7:3₂₀ fiber mats showed a slightly increased viability of ST-2 cells after a three-day incubation period compared to NF7:3 and NF7:3_{30D} samples, respectively, with a significant difference of $p < 0.05$ for the investigated samples. Moreover, storage conditions (30 days at -20 °C) of the PCL/CS/κ-C solution used to produce the NF7:3_{30D} fiber mats did not show any negative impact on its cellular activity. No change in mitochondrial activity compared to the other PCL/CS/κ-C fibers could be detected after the incubation period. However, after seven days, a considerable increase in the measured cell viability was observed for NF7:3₂₀ and NF7:3_{30D} samples relative to NF7:3 fiber mats. A lower cell viability of NF7:3 can be attributed to the storage conditions after its fabrication and the effect of factors such as temperature, humidity and time, being the first fiber

mat to have been produced and being stored in aluminum foil at room temperature without any special storage condition. In this sense, the effect of storage conditions at different time periods after the production of electrospun fibers could be another important parameter to study in the future. The absence of cytotoxicity demonstrated by N7:3_30D in comparison to the other specimens investigated suggests that stable and suitable fiber mats for bone tissue engineering and wound healing applications can be produced from PCL/CS/ κ -C polymer solutions containing 7:3 ratio of FA/AA after being stored for 30 days at -20°C . Finally, the increase in cell viability of NF7:3_20 may be associated with the use of a higher voltage (20 kV) during the preparation of this electrospun fiber mat in accordance with the results reported by Can-Herrera *et al* [60]. They studied PCL

electrospun fibers at different voltages, obtaining an increase in fiber diameter and surface roughness as voltage increased, explaining that these parameters play a key role in the cellular response and can promote a better anchorage of the cells to the substrate.

The SEM micrographs in figures 7(A)–(C) (upper two rows) show elongated cells on the surface of the fibrillar structures, indicating both cell adhesion and proliferation. Quantitative proliferation data of ST-2 cells was further validated by fluorescent micrographs of cells. Figures 7(A)–(C) (lower two rows) shows the stained F-actin cytoskeletons (red, phalloidin) and cell nuclei (blue, DAPI) as well as living cells (green, Calcein-AM) of the specimens after seven days of incubation. On the NF7:3 fiber mat the cells grew in lower density (figure 7(A)), and exhibited lower intersected connections. On the other hand,

Figure 8. SEM micrographs of ST-2 cells interacting with needle-type structures generated by PCL/CS/ κ -C fiber mats after seven days of incubation. (A) NF7:3, (B) NF7:3_20 and (C) NF7:3_30D, where the additional formation of well-defined nanospheres is observed (higher magnification micrograph).

N7:3_20 and N7:3_30D samples showed higher cell density (figures 7(B) and (C)) with more intersected connections, supporting the results obtained for the cell viability after seven days of incubation (see figure 6).

SEM micrographs in figure 8(A) show the behavior of ST-2 cells seeded on NF7:3 nanofibers for seven days in RPMI cell culture medium. The fiber mats were able to produce a needle-type structure after seven days of incubation. However, NF7:3_20 (figure 8(B)) and NF7:3_30D (figure 8(C)) additionally originated clusters of particles from these structures, but only NF7:3_30D was capable of eventually transforming these particles into well-defined nanospheres with diameters below 200 nm (figure 8(C)). Similar spherical nanoparticles were reported by Saremi *et al* [61], where thiolated CS nanoparticles for enhancing oral absorption of docetaxel were synthesized via radical emulsion polymerization. From the

bioactivity and degradation tests, it can be inferred that the nanoparticles emerged as a by-product of degradation/release of CS and κ -C into the cell culture medium due to distinct biological properties of these biopolymers [34]. Accordingly, the moderate bioactive behavior observed in the previous assays became more evident when the direct cell viability assay was performed and evaluated. In consequence, the NF7:3_30D sample in contact with both cells and medium induced a higher response, generating crystal-type structures in a shorter period of time.

4. Conclusions

Electrospun blend nanofiber mats containing PCL, chitosan and κ -carrageenan (PCL/CS/ κ -C) were successfully fabricated by varying the FA/AA ratio in the solvent system. The ratio of FA/AA played an important role in the final properties of the fiber mats,

demonstrating that a ratio of 7:3 exhibited the most promising features such as increased wettability and Young's modulus. The polymer solution was found to be stable under storage conditions of -20°C for 30 days and thus, it was considered to be suitable for producing electrospun nanofibers after a longer period of storage time. The immersion of the NF7:3 samples in different media indicated a possible bioactive response. Moreover, no cytotoxic effects were observed by cell viability measurements. Cells seeded on samples were able to proliferate over time and spread on the fibers. The addition of κ -C significantly enhanced the solubility of the polymers that in combination with HMW CS provided the stability that the solution required to be stored at -20°C for a long period without affecting the biological response and hardly compromising the mechanical properties of the obtained electrospun fiber mats. The developed CS and κ -C containing PCL fibers with mineralization capability should be further investigated for applications in bone tissue engineering and wound healing applications.

Data availability statement

All data that support the findings of this study are included within the article (and any supplementary files).

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